

Dehydrogenation of Five- and Six-membered Cyclanes in the Presence of Activated Carbon

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Activated birchwood carbon has been shown capable of dehydrogenating five- and six-membered cyclanes at elevated temperatures with the formation of dehydrogenation products in high yields. At 600° the extent of conversion of cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane to the aromatic hydrocarbons reaches a value to 97% and 100% respectively; cyclopentane and methylcyclopentane under these conditions are converted into the corresponding cyclopentadienes in yields up to 29%.

Several investigations have shown that activated carbon is capable of catalysing a diversity of reactions. Thus it is known to bring about the dehydrogenation of terpenes (Rudakov *et al.*, *Z. Prikladn. Khim.*, 1949, 12, 180), the irreversible catalysis of cyclohexane (Zelinsky *et al.*, *Izvestia Acad. Nauk, U.S.S.R., O. Kh. N.*, 1951, 819), the dehydrogenation of alkylidihydrofuranes (Belsky, *Doklady Acad. Nauk, U.S.S.R.*, 1960, 132, 585), etc.

Recently we have demonstrated that dehydrogenation of five-membered cyclanes to the corresponding cyclopentadienes can be accomplished at 500-600° under reduced pressure by various types of activated carbons, such as, birchwood carbon with grain diameter of 5-6 mm, fine grained "BAU", and bone charcoal (Shuikin *et al.*, *ibid.*, in print).

There are no references in the literature to the possibility of dehydrogenating five-membered cyclanes by means of this catalyst. With respect to the six-membered compounds, Moldavsky and collaborators (*Zhur. Obs. Khim.*, 1937, 7, 1840) have shown that cyclohexane, passed with a space velocity of 0.14 hr.⁻¹ over birchwood carbon at 533°, yielded 17% benzene; at 560° the yield was 56.1%.

These and previous observations encouraged us to proceed on to a more detailed investigation of the catalytic properties of activated wood carbon with regard to the dehydrogenation of five- and six-membered cyclanes.

We found activated carbon to convert the six-membered cyclanes into the corresponding dehydrogenation products in almost quantitative yields. Thus at 600°, under ordinary pressure, cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane are converted to the extent of 97% and 100% respectively:

As is well known, dehydrogenation of six-membered cyclanes to the corresponding aromatic hydrocarbons takes place smoothly according to Zelinsky's method (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 3678) on

Pt-carbon at 300°. Under such conditions the predominant role, however, is played by the finely dispersed platinum of which the content in the catalyst at first amounted to 30% (Zelinsky and Shuikin, *Z. Obs. Khim.*, 1934, 4, 901; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1935, 27, 1209; *Z. Prikladn. Khim.*, 1936, 9, 260) and only later was lowered to 4% (Shuikin, *Uspekhi Khim.*, 1946, 15, 343). Since five-membered rings did not undergo dehydrogenation at 300°, Zelinsky called this reaction of the six-membered compounds in the presence of platinum and palladium "selective catalysis" (*loc. cit.*).

We have shown that cyclopentane and methylcyclopentane at 600° under reduced pressure of 10-15 mm on contact with activated carbon gave 18% and 29% yields of the respective cyclopentadienes:

In the absence of activated carbon, cyclopentane and methylcyclopentane did not undergo dehydrogenation at 600°; among the thermal conversion products of cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane, the aromatics were present only to the extent of 6%. When the thermal reactions are compared with the high extent of conversion in the presence of activated birchwood carbon, one can see how great is the activity of the latter in the reaction under question.

EXPERIMENTAL

Initial Hydrocarbons

Cyclopentane (b.p. 49.5°/754 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4070, d_4^{20} 0.7459) was prepared by hydrogenation of cyclopentene, which in turn had been synthesised by dehydration of cyclopentanol over anhydrous magnesium sulphate at 310°:

Methylcyclopentane (b.p. 72°/759 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4100, d_4^{20} 0.7492) was obtained by isomerisation of cyclohexane (b.p. 80.8°/758 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4262; d_4^{20} 0.7787), slowly distilled over aluminium chloride in a continuous distillation column of 20 HETP efficiency.

Methylcyclohexane (b.p. 101°/757 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4231, d_4^{20} 0.7698).—Activated wood carbon of specific surface 519 m²/g. and ash content of 0.48% served as the catalyst. In runs without the catalyst, the glass reactor was packed with pieces of broken quartz. The reactants were passed through at rates 0.3-0.1 hr.⁻¹. The cyclopentadiene hydrocarbon content of the resultants was determined directly after dehydrogenation of the five-membered cyclanes (Afanasiev, *Zavodskaja Lab.*, 1948, No. 12, 1942). The aromatic hydrocarbon of the cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane catalysates was determined refractometrically after distillation over metallic sodium (Zelinsky and Pavlov, *Z. Russ. Khim. Obsch.*, 1926, 58, 1309).

The results of the experiments on the dehydrogenation of five- and six-membered cyclanes in the presence of activated birchwood carbon are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Dehydrogenation of five- and six-membered cyclanes on activated carbon.

Reactant.	Pressure.	Temp.	Flow rate (hr. ⁻¹).	Catalysate yield.	n_D^{20} of catalysate.	Dehydro- genation products in catalysate.
Catalyst : Activated birchwood carbon.						
Cyclopentane	10 mm	550°	0.1	84.0%	1.4140	14%
"	10	600°	0.1	81.7	1.4180	18
Methylcyclopentane	10	500°	0.1	90.2	1.4230	11
"	12	550°	0.1	89.4	1.4245	16
"	15	600°	0.1	84.1	1.4295	29
Cyclohexane	755	500°	0.3	80.4	1.4723	70
"	754	500°	0.1	79.9	1.4775	76
"	754	550°	0.1	79.0	1.4808	82
"	756	600°	0.3	76.1	1.4940	93
"	754	600°	0.1	75.3	1.4977	97
Methylcyclohexane	756	500°	0.1	81.2	1.4513	44
"	756	550°	0.1	74.2	1.4935	95
"	756	600°	0.1	74.8	1.4970	100
Catalyst : Nil.						
Cyclopentane	15	600°	0.1	90.9	1.4070	0
Methylcyclopentane	15	600°	0.1	88.1	1.4100	0
Cyclohexane	758	550°	0.1	77.9	1.4262	0
"	758	600°	0.1	74.3	1.4290	6
Methylcyclohexane	750	500°	0.1	81.2	1.4233	0
"	750	550°	0.1	71.5	1.4242	2
"	750	600°	0.1	70.1	1.4265	6

It appears from the table that cyclopentane and methylcyclopentane are dehydrogenated to the corresponding cyclopentadiene hydrocarbons, the contents of the latter in the catalysate of the run at 600°, flow rate 0.1 hr.⁻¹, and pressure 10-15 mm being 18% and 29% respectively. The extent of dehydrogenation of cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane to aromatic hydrocarbons at the same temperature but at ordinary pressure attains a value of 97-100%. Dehydrogenation of cyclohexane at 500° and space velocity 0.3 yields a catalysate with 70% benzene content while at 600° and the same velocity, the content of benzene reaches 93%.

From the experimental results the temperature appears to be a factor exerting considerable influence on the yield of the dehydrogenation products. Thus on raising the temperature from 500° to 600°, the yield in aromatics on dehydrogenation of cyclohexane increases by 23-21% and the extent of dehydrogenation of methylcyclopentane by more than 2.5 times. Of less importance is the flow velocity of the reactant hydrocarbons. Thus with a decrease in space velocity of cyclohexane by 3 times, from 0.3 to 0.1 hr.⁻¹, the benzene content increased only from 93 to 97%.

It should be mentioned that in the cyclohexane catalysate (b.p. 78-80° at 759 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4970, d_4^{20} 0.8768), obtained at 600° by means of gas-liquid chromatography, besides benzene

only the original cyclohexane in amounts of about 3% was detected. At the same time in the methylcyclohexane catalysate, together with toluene up to 20% benzene could be determined. This provides experimental evidence that under the chosen conditions demethylation of toluene to benzene takes place as a side reaction. In subsequent work we intend to investigate further the catalytic action of activated carbon.

The control experiments carried out without a catalyst showed that at 600° cyclopentane and methylcyclopentane do not undergo dehydrogenation to any noticeable degree. Cyclohexane passed through the reactor at 550° under thermal reaction conditions also came out unchanged; the cyclohexane catalysate, however, obtained in the 600° run possessed a benzene content of 6%. At the same time in the methylcyclohexane catalysate, toluene was detected already in the runs at 550°, although the amounts were insignificant (ca. 2%). In the 600° runs the toluene content of the catalysate was 6%.

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